

Mola mola Ocean sunfish

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Bony fish

Size: The species length is up to 2 metres

Distribution:

Circumglobally found in tropical and sub-tropical waters. Found in all oceans, including the Atlantic, Indian and Pacific oceans.

Importance:

The Ocean sunfish is described as one of the heaviest bony fish in the world, with a sister species recorded as the heaviest bony fish. It forms part of the large iconic sunfish group seen by many water users. Furthermore, the species forms part of the mid-water trawling bycatch. Knowledge of this specific species is important for sustainable fisheries management and understanding the phylogeny in South African waters.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 70.68 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.19 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.63 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.9% [Single: 97.3%, Duplicated: 1.6%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 6 633 kilobases

Contig number: 2 094

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